

Studies in the Formation and Properties of Carbon-Oxygen Surface Complexes : Part II. Nature of the Surface Complexes Formed on Progressive Treatment with Oxidising Solutions

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Treatments of 1000°-outgassed sugar charcoal with increasing amounts of nitric acid as well as with aqueous solution of chlorine, potassium persulphate and hydrogen peroxide result in chemisorption of increasing amounts of oxygen giving rise mostly to CO₂-complex and in the case of the first two treatments also to concomitant increase in surface area and gasification of carbon. The complex formed initially is largely non-acidic, formed by the chemisorption of oxygen at unsaturated sites, but in later stages it is acidic formed by the association of two atoms of oxygen per active surface carbon atom. The continued treatment also causes conversion of non-acidic into acidic complex as well as disappearance of unsaturated sites and gasification of carbon. A suitable mechanism for these phenomena has been suggested.

The formation of two types of carbon-oxygen surface complexes, each capable of evolving carbon dioxide when evacuated at high temperatures, on treatment of outgassed charcoals with oxidising solutions, has been indicated in some previous work from these laboratories^{1,2}. One of these complexes is acidic and titratable against alkalis and is supposed to be formed by the association of two oxygen atoms per active surface carbon atom^{1,2} located at some of the active centres on the surface while the second complex is neutral in character and is supposed to be formed by chemisorption of oxygen at the unsaturated sites created by elimination of combined oxygen during outgassing⁴. The present paper describes the effect of giving a prolonged treatment to sugar charcoal, outgassed at 1000°, with various oxidising solutions on the formation of these two types of complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal prepared and outgassed in the manner described before⁴ was used in these investigations. Five g. portions were given repeated treatments with aqueous solutions of (a) chlorine (0.05 *N*), (b) potassium persulphate (nearly saturated in 2 NH₂SO₄) and (c) hydrogen peroxide (3 *N*), as described before¹, as well as with (d) hot concentrated nitric acid⁵. In the case of the first three treatments, the supernatant liquid was siphoned off after every 24 hours of shaking and a fresh lot was added. This was continued for 48 days. The treatment with nitric acid consisted in mixing 10 g. portions with increasing amounts, varying from 10 ml. to

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2. B. R. Puri, Proc. Fifth Carbon Conf., Pergamon Press, pp. 165-1962.
3. W. E. Garner, and D. McKie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2451.

300 ml. of the acid and heating the mixture, as described before⁵. The amounts of oxygen chemisorbed after every 4 or more treatments with the first three treatments and after every treatment with nitric acid were determined by estimating the amounts of CO and CO₂ evolved on outgassing the treated materials (after careful washing and drying) at 1200° in the usual manner⁴.

The base adsorption capacity was determined by titrating against 0.25 N barium hydroxide, and surface unsaturation by treatment with aqueous bromine⁴.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amounts of oxygen chemisorbed on repeated treatments with various oxidising solutions or with increasing amounts of nitric acid and evolved either as carbon dioxide or carbon monoxide are plotted graphically in figs. 1 and 2. It is seen

Fig. 2.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Chemisorption of oxygen and its disposal as carbon monoxide and carbon-dioxide on continued treatments with various oxidising solutions.

Fig. 2. Chemisorption of oxygen and its disposal as carbon monoxide and carbon-dioxide on treatments with increasing amounts of nitric acid.

that most of the oxygen is evolved as carbon dioxide and only small amounts, that too on treatments with chlorine water and nitric acid, are evolved as carbon monoxide. It is also seen that maximum values of oxygen chemisorbed are much more with nitric acid and chlorine water than with hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate and are attained in a much longer period.

In the case of treatments with nitric acid there was a gradual concomitant increase in surface area, as measured by moisture adsorption⁶, and also an appreciable gasification as indicated by loss in weight (cf. Table 1.) The increase in surface area

4. B. R. Puri, N. K. Sandle and O. P. Mahajan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.

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TABLE I

Treatment of 1000°-outgassed sugar charcoal with various oxidising solutions

	Surface area (m ² /g)	CO ₂ -evolved on outgassing at 1200° (m.e./100 g.)	Barium hydroxide neutralised (m.e./100 g.)	Non-titratable CO ₂ -complex (m.e./100g.)	Percentage of titratable CO ₂ -complex (%)	Fixation of bromine (m.e./100g.)	Loss in weight dur- ing treat- ment (%)
No treatment	412	nil	nil	—	—	398	—
<i>Treatment with HNO₃</i>							
1 ml./g.	—	265	10	255	3.7	125	2.5
3 „	—	317	40	277	12.5	108	6.0
5 „	—	396	59	337	15.0	66	9.8
8 „	450	445	79	366	17.8	28	17.4
10 „	—	560	188	372	33.5	18	22.5
15 „	465	869	488	381	56.7	nil	—
20 „	485	1025	780	245	76.0	nil	40.8
25 „	—	1085	995	90	93.4	nil	—
30 „	526	1175	1170	nil	100	nil	70.0
<i>Treatment with chlorine water</i>							
4 Treatments	—	185	70	115 (35)*	37.6	240	—
8 „	415	258	120	138 (40)*	46.5	203	3.2
12 „	418	350	181	169 (44)*	51.7	175	4.8
16 „	—	462	213	249.0 (44)*	46.1	105	6.4
20 „	—	645	233	412	36.1	nil	8.5
24 „	425	700	312	388	44.6	nil	10.5
28 „	—	738	359	379	47.7	nil	—
32 „	435	764	478	286	61.1	nil	14.8
36 „	—	784	505	279	63.5	nil	18.0
42 „	445	810	607	203	73.4	nil	—
48 „	—	829	733	96	88.4	nil	24.0
<i>Treatment with potassium persulphate</i>							
4 Treatments	415	160	15	145	9.4	246	0.1
8 „	410	173	20	153	11.5	240	0.3
12 „	—	167	20	147	11.9	240	0.8
20 „	414	185	25	160	13.5	230	1.2
32 „	—	195	28	167	14.4	218	1.5
48 „	415	195	30	165	15.4	223	1.8
<i>Treatment with hydrogen peroxide</i>							
4 „	412	205	30	175	14.6	212	nil
8 „	—	225	40	185	17.8	205	nil
16 „	416	240	40	200	16.7	200	nil
24 „	—	275	50	225	18.2	180	nil
32 „	415	290	65	225	22.4	178	nil
48 „	—	295	69	226	23.4	175	nil

* Chlorine fixed (m.e./100 g.)

appears to be due to gasification which causes etching and creation of more kinks and corners. These effects were relatively less on treatment with aqueous chlorine and almost absent with hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate.

The values of surface acidity as measured by barium hydroxide values and the values of carbon dioxide evolved, expressed in similar units, are also given in Table I. The difference between the two, whenever in excess of 2 per cent, was taken as the amount of non-acidic complex formed, as before¹. These values are given in a separate column. The bromine value, which is taken as a measure of surface unsaturation⁴, is seen to fall progressively with increase in the amount of non-acidic complex formed, the fall being almost equal to the increase in non-acidic CO₂-complex, till it becomes zero. However, in the case of chlorine treated samples, the fall in bromine values is relatively more. This appears to be due to simultaneous fixation of chlorine as well, the values for which are given in the parentheses. These observations confirm that the non-acidic complex is formed at the unsaturated sites.

It appears from the data that in the initial stages more of the oxygen is chemisorbed in the form of non-acidic complex and a relatively small amount of acidic complex is formed. As the treatment is continued with strong oxidising agents, such as nitric acid and chlorine water, the greater proportion of the additional oxygen is fixed as acidic complex. Beyond a certain stage, the amount of non-acidic CO₂-complex starts decreasing. At the same time the increase in the amount of the acidic complex is much more than the amount of additional oxygen fixed. It follows, therefore, that the continued treatment with these reagents cause not only fixation of more and more oxygen at the active sites capable of forming acidic complex but also progressive conversion of non-acidic into acidic complex, till most, if not the entire oxygen, is present as acidic complex. However, the unsaturated sites previously occupied by the non-acidic complex are not revived again.

The formation of non-acidic complex on outgassed charcoals, by the oxidation of unsaturated sites has been represented as under :

where the circle represents the charcoal surface and ---C and ---C two surface carbon atoms. The conversion of this complex into the acidic complex, according to the structure assigned to the latter^{1,3}, with simultaneous disappearance of unsaturated sites, accompanied by gasification, on continued treatment with increasing amounts of oxygen, may be represented as :

The fact that there is a considerable loss of carbon in the range in which non-acidic complex changes into acidic complex offers support to the above view. The continued treatment would result ultimately in the stripping off of this oxide layer as gaseous carbon dioxide.

The work reported in this paper is useful in elucidating the nature and structure of surface oxides of carbon about which opinions differ so widely at present ^{7, 8, 9}. It also throws considerable light on the mechanism of low temperature gasification.

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